

MANAGING DERANGED RFT THROUGH AYURVEDA- A CASE REPORT**Dr. Anurag Kushal*¹, Dr. Ritika Verma²**¹*Assistant Professor, Department of Panchkarma, National Institute of Ayurveda Panchkula.²Associate Professor, Department of Samhita and Siddhant, Shree Dhanwantry Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Chandigarh.

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Corresponding Author*Dr. Anurag Kushal**

Assistant Professor, Department of
Panchkarma, National Institute of
Ayurveda Panchkula.

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ABSTRACT

Kidneys play an important role in excretion, hormone production and regulation of extracellular fluid volume. Renal function tests are useful for identifying the presence of renal disease, its progression and response to management. Gout represents of uric acid disturbance which is divided into asymptomatic hyperurecemia acute gouty arthritis, intercritical period, and chronic tophaceous gout. Diagnosis is based on laboratory and radiological features. Contemporary science focus on managing flares, chronic gout and prevention of flares, as well comorbidities. Also, patient education, diet and life style changes plays important role. Ayurveda compares it with Vatarakta which suggests vitiation of Vata Dosha and Rakta Dhatu (blood). In this study, the patient was treated with oral medications. Improvement in quality of life and RFT was reported in 45 days. This case report provides guidelines that gout and derranged RFT can be managed in Ayurveda.

KEYWORDS: Capsule 6V Gout, Derranged RFT, Punarnavashataka Kwath, Uricacid.**INTRODUCTION**

Kidneys are two bean-shaped organs playing an important role in excretion, hormone production (erythropoietin, 1,25 dihydroxy vitamin D, and renin) and regulation of extracellular fluid volume. Nephron is functional unit of the kidney. Renal function tests are useful for identifying the presence of renal diseas, its progression and response to

management.^[1] Gout represents disturbed uric acid which is divided into asymptomatic hyperuricemia, acute gouty arthritis, intercritical period, and chronic tophaceous gout.^[2] Diagnosis is based on laboratory and radiological features. Contemporary science focus on managing flares, chronic gout and prevention of flares, as well comorbidities. Also, patient education, diet and life style changes plays important role. Ayurveda compares it with Vatarakta which suggests vitiation of Vata Dosha and Rakta Dhatu (blood). Also, the physiology of urine formation as per ayurveda texts explains that *Kitta Bhaga* is divided into two parts- one is water content (Mutra) and other part is solid content (stool). The water content of Kitta after absorption from Pakvashaya (large intestine) is further described as Mutra bhaga (urine).^[3]

Present case is a diagnosed case of Parkinsonism with deranged Renal Function Tests and was managed with Ayurvedic medications.

CASE STUDY

A 62 year old Male Patient came in OPD with the symptoms of

- Pain in toes and ankle joint
- Puffy face, eye's
- Breathlessness
- Frothy Urine
- Anorexia
- Constipation
- History of Present Illness- Patient was apparently alright 4 year before. He is a known case of Parkinsonism. Taking Levodopa and carbi dopa 100/25 mg twice a day. Gradually he experience Pain in toes and ankle joint, puffyness on face, leg and frothy urine.

Past History- Known case of Parkinsonism, No Hypertyension, Diabetes Mellitus, Stroke, Ischemic heart disease, Tuberculosis, Bronchial Asthma.

Personal History- Married, non smoker, non alcoholic.

Family History- Both Father and mother suffered from Hypertension.

Ashtvidha Pariksha- Table 1.

Sr. No.	Pariksha	Feature
1	Nadi	76/min
2	Mala	Vibandha (Constipated)
3	Mutra	Yellow Colored
4	Jivha	Saam (Coated)
5	Shabda	Normal
6	Sparsh	Ushna (Slightly raised body temperature)
7	Drik	Yellow coloured
8	Akriti	Medium built

MATERIAL AND METHOD**a. Method**

- Center of study: NIA hospital, Panchkula
- Case Study.

b. Material- Table 2. Duration was 1 ½ months.

Sr. No	Name Of Drug	Dose of Drug	Kala	Frequency	Anupan
1	Punarnavashtaka Kwath	20 ml	Prag bhakt	Twice a day	-
	Ark Makoye	20 ml			
3	Capsule 6VGout	1 cap	Adhobhakt	Twice a day	Ushnodaka
4	Ashwagandha churna	3 gm	Adhobhakt	Twice a day	Ushnodaka
	Kronch Beej Churna	2 gm			
5	Kutki Powder	2 gm	Nisha kaal	Once a day At night	Ushnodaka
	Nishoth Powder	2 gm			
	Haritki Powder	1 gm			

RESULT**Table 3.**

Sr. No.	Pariksha	Before Treatment (15/11/25)	After Treatment (1/1/2026)
1	Blood Urea	60 mg/dl	36 mg/dl
2	Serum Creatinine	1.45 mg/dl	1.20 mg/dl
3	Serum Uric Acid	11.3 mg/dl	8.7 mg/dl

Table 4.

Sr. No.	Symptoms	Before Treatment (15/11/25)	After Treatment (1/1/2026)
1	Pain in toes and ankle joint	VAS-8	VAS-3
2	Puffy face, eye's	+	-
3	Breathlessness	+	-
4	Frothy Urine	++	-
5	Anorexia	+++	-
6	Constipation	+++	-

DISCUSSION

As per ayurveda texts, after digestion, *Sara* and *Kitta* portions are formed. In Pakvashaya, the *Kitta* portion further gets converted into *Purisha* and *Mutra* after which it moves to Basti and expelled out through Mootravahasrotasa. *Apaanavaayu* control process of excretion. Hence, *Shothhara*, *Vaat Anulomak* and *Mutral* medicines were used here.^[4]

Punarnavashtaka Kwath^[5]

- a. *Tikta*, *Kashaya* and *Madhura Rasa*, *Laghu guna* and *Ushna virya*.
- b. Beta sitosterol is one of active principle which metabolize cholesterol, anti-inflammatory, hence Reduce burning micturition and improves urine output.

Ark Makoye^{[6][7][8]} (*Solanum nigrum*)

- a. Makoye is *Laghu*, *Snigdha*, *Katu vipaka*, *Tikta rasa*, *anushna virya* and *tridoshghana*.
- b. It is Shoth hara and indicated in *jwara*, *yakrit vikaar*, *pandu*, *kamla arsha*.
- c. Methnol extract and SNFET are having Nephroprotective activity.

Ashwagandha churna^{[9][10]}

- a. It is *Laghu Snigdha Guna*, *Madhur Vipaka*, *Ushna Virya*, *Tikta*, *Madhur*, *Katu Rasa* and *KaphaVata Shamaka*.
- b. Aswagandha has neuroprotective phytoconstituents like sitoindosides VII–X, withaferin A, withanosides IV, withanols, withanolide A, withanolide B, anaferine, beta-sitosterol, withanolide D. Hence it can be used in brain disorders mainly anxiety, Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, Schizophrenia, Huntington's disease, dyslexia, depression, autism, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder etc.

Kronch Beej Churna^{[11][12]}

- a. *Guru Snigdha*, *Madhura Tikta Rasa*, *Madhura Vipaka*, *Ushna Virya*, *Vata Shamaka*, *Kapha Pitta Vardhaka*.
- b. Kapikachhu's phytochemicals are neuroprotective. They possess anti-inflammatory properties, modulating immune responses and reducing the production of inflammatory mediators which is crucial in preserving dopaminergic neurons and sustaining dopamine levels, which further helps in managing Parkinsons Disease symptoms.

Kutki Powder^{[13][14]}

- a. *Laghu, Ruksha, Tikts Rasa, Katu Vipaka, Sheet Virya Kapha Pitta hara and Pitta Virechaka.*
- b. Picrolivis obtained from 3 - 4 years old roots and rhizomes of *Picrorhiza kurroa* (kutki) is used mainly for the treatment of a variety of liver ailments. It is an iridoid glycoside mixture containing 60% picroside I and kutkoside.

Nishoth Powder^{[15][16]}

- a. *Lagu, Ruksha Tikshna guna, Katu Tikta Rasa, Katu vipaka, Ushna virya and Sukhvirechaka.*
- b. Several phyto-constituents, including α - and β -turpethin, turpethinic acids, lanosta-5-ene, etc are present in this plant. It has anti-tumor, anti-fungal, anti-hypertensive, asthma inhibitor, anti-ulcer, and antioxidant actions.

Haritki Powder^{[17][18]}

- a. *Laghu Ruksha guna, Panchrasayukta lavan varjit, Madhur vipaka, Ushna Virya and Anulomaka.*
- b. Aqueous extract, Ethanolic extract, Triethylchebulate etc are some of active compounds. It is Antioxident, Antimicrobial, Antimutagenic, Antiarthritic, Cytoprotective etc. in action.

Capsule 6V Gout- Table 5.

Medicine	Contents	Probable mode of action
6v gout	Ext. Giloy (1:10) (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>) 200 mg	Guduchi ^{[19][20]} contains alkaloids such as berberine, diterpenoid lactones, glycosides and polysaccharides having uricosuric activity. Guduchi being Tridosahara with TiktaRasa, possessing anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties. Hence 6V Gout helps in reducing Uric acid.
	Guggulu Purified (<i>Communiphora mukul</i>) 200 mg	
	Ext. Suranjan Kadea (1:5) (<i>Colchicum luteum</i>) 120 mg	
	Ext. Haritaki (1:2) (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>) 40 mg	
	Ext. Bibhitaki (1:2) (<i>Terminalia belerica</i>) 40 mg	
	Ext. Amlaki (1:3) (<i>Embilica officinalis</i>) 40 mg	
	Sunthi (<i>Zingiber officinalis</i>) 40 mg	
	Marica (<i>Piper nigrum</i>) 40 mg	
	Pippali (<i>Piper longum</i>) 40 mg	
	Trivrt (<i>Operculina turpethum</i>) 40 mg	

CONCLUSION

This study suggests that derranged RFT can be improved with Ayurveda medications. *Vaat-anuloman* is also necessary in these type of patients. This is a single case study shows good results. Further more study are needed in large scale with large sample size.

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